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Religious Doctrine or Socio-Political Grievance? A Critical Analysis of Terrorism in the Context of Islam

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Abstract

The concept of “terrorism” has gained popularity in the post-9/11 era, with increased scrutiny on its associations with Islamic religious doctrines. The increased emphasis has frequently resulted in the confusion between Islam and terrorism. This phenomenon obliterates the intricate interactions between socio-political, theological, and economic elements that incite terrorism. This paper examined the fundamental causes of terrorism and how religion could be instrumentalized as a justification for violence. This study aims to identify the socio-political factors that underpin terrorism and to assess the extent to which religion is instrumentalized within extremist sentiments. Although religious justification is frequently used, preliminary research indicates that the primary drivers of terrorist activity are often socio-political. However, there is a need for updated scrutiny of the religiosity claimed by various terrorist organizations, due to their analogous natures. This paper employed a comparative case study approach as a qualitative research method, focusing on ISIS and Boko Haram as case studies. Analyzing these two organizations allows for a deeper understanding of how religious discourse intersects with socio-political grievances, thereby illuminating the complexities of their ideologies and recruitment strategies. This study sought to clarify the misconceptions surrounding the religion-terrorism nexus by emphasizing the importance of re-evaluating the phenomenon of terrorist groups not solely through their professed religious ideologies but also through their socio-political contexts.

Keywords: Religious Doctrine, Islam, Terrorism, Socio-political grievances, Boko Haram, ISIS

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Introduction

Terrorism has undergone a profound evolution in the twentieth-century global landscape in terms of definition as well as its scope. Originally applied to state terrorism, where the French Revolution’s Reign of Terror can be recounted as an example, the concept has broadened to include political violence implemented by non-state actors. In this period especially after the September 11, 2001 attack on the USA, terrorism is equated with religious fundamentalism, and the Islamic scriptures are widely held as having alibi for terrorism. This perception has not only influenced the public philosophy in the given world but also the counter-terrorism policies all over the world with the assistance of strengthening the belief in the existence of some kind of link between Islam and terrorism. However, such a manner of tying them basic might lead to overlooking or even erasing the socio-political, economic, and cultural factors that play into the encouragement and sustenance of terrorism.

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The first instances of violence under the guise of religion date to the zealots of ancient Judaism, the medieval Assassins, and the Catholic Church's Inquisition. These incidents signify the fact that religion has been instrumentalized for ages to justify violence for political purposes. In contemporary times, organizations like ISIS and Boko Haram inherited this legacy by using Islamic scriptures to recruit followers and hunt their adversaries. However, analytical scrutiny reveals that these organizations unswervingly exploit socio-political discrimination, unfair economic distribution, political oppression, and social marginalization as the driving causes of extremism. Hence, religion is not used to cause violence but as a tool for mobilization or for constituting the agenda for diverse interests.

In this respect, this study seeks to investigate the relationship between terrorism and Islam and evaluate to what extent socio-political factors contribute as compared to religion in escalating extremism. This study employs a comparative case study method to analyze the religious doctrines professed by ISIS, and the socio-political dimensions underlying the emergence of Boko Haram. Although these two terrorist groups have some similarities in terms of ideologies and political goals, studies have shown that ISIS is more prevalent in its religious sentiments, whereas Boko Haram is more inclined to its socio-economic and political interests (Yahaya, 2016). Through analyzing these two cases, it is possible to assess some different motives of terrorism ranging from ideological manipulation and socio-political factors and economic inequalities. Based on the aim of this study, an extensive literature review of the term terrorism, its relationship with religion, and how religion is instrumentalized as a justification for terrorist acts is analyzed. Using immanent critique to counter its claims, the ideology professed by the pseudo-religious ISIS was also examined. Boko Haram, which turned into a full-fledged terrorist group after the death of its founder in 2009 was also analyzed through the lens of the political instabilities in Northern Nigeria. The study emphasizes the importance of re-evaluating the "religion-terrorism nexus" by situating terrorism within its broader social, economic, and political landscapes. The paper concludes its analysis by giving recommendations on how to approach not only ISIS and Boko Haram but also other groups operating under the guise of religion, destroying life and property. Through this analysis, this paper contributes to ongoing debates on the roots of terrorism and the role of religion in modern global terrorism.

Defining Terrorism

The term "terrorism" has become so pervasive that it is encountered on a frequent basis by nearly every individual within the global community. Although this concept gained momentum as an academic discipline in the 1960s, its first usage in a secular context can be traced back to the 18th and 19th centuries, when the French Academy used the word to describe the Reign of Terror in the period of the French Revolution (Mahir & Serkan, 2019). Terrorism at that time had a positive meaning, as opposed to the meaning given to terrorism today. It was a reference to the widespread campaign of violence against the front-line Jacobins, spearheaded by France (Linton, 2023). However, literature shows us that the concept of terror dates to antiquity. In 105 B.C., the term "terror cimbricus" was coined in ancient Rome to describe the widespread panic and state of emergency that arose as the Cimbri tribe's warriors advanced towards the city (Shanice, 2019). The first instances of terror prior to the modern era were predominantly executed in the context of religion. The Zealots, alongside their extremist offshoot, the Sicarii, are acknowledged to be the first terrorist organizations in history, having existed in the 1st century A.D (Horsley, 1986). Zealotry was an ancient Jewish movement distinguished by its religious

conservatism and its resistance to the Roman authority. The movement aimed to create Jewish theocracy by using brutal tactics including attacking Jewish towns and abducting wealthy Jews, severing the food supply in Jerusalem to stir revolt, and killing Roman loyalists with tiny, disguised daggers. The movement lasted until 70 A.D. (Mahir & Serkan, 2019). Another terrorist movement that operated under the guise of religion was the Assassin group, formed by Hassan-i Sabbah in 1090. There are arguments that this group had connections to the Batiniyya cult of the Ismaili sect. This group was well-known for operating by assassinating the frontbenchers of their enemy states. Their militants, who were known as Fedayeen, were castrated to prevent them from becoming sidetracked by sexual interests or familial responsibilities. If apprehended, Fedayeen either committed suicide with the opium they brought or were killed by other members in order to keep the group's secrets (Amir, 2024). The Inquisition which was institutionalized and practiced by the Catholic Church from the 11th to the 19th century is also considered a form of violence and terrorism executed in the context of religion (Eroğlu, 2004, pp. 93–100). During the Inquisition, people who were thought to have gone against the Catholic dogma were labeled as heretics. They were excommunicated at first, then turned over to secular tribunals where they were put to death, usually by drowning or auto-da-fé. As a result of these applications, thousands of Muslims and Jews were executed by burning, especially in Spain by the 16th century (Eroğlu, 2004, p. 98).

As we have mentioned earlier, the word “terrorism” is a product of modernity. With time, the meanings given to this word have undergone several changes. The most notable shift is the transition of the terrorism paradigm from state actors to non-state actors. The various dimensions associated with the concept have rendered its definition somewhat complex in literature. According to Schmidt (2023), the complexity of defining terrorism can be approached by reviewing the history of terrorism, the psychology of ‘terror’, forms of political violence, terrorist acts, and the terrorism carried out. Another notable definition in literature was done by Başeren (2006), who examines the concept of terrorism by utilizing parameters like motive, instrument, goal, and intent. Motive refers to the reasons which drive the actions of the terrorists.

The violent act itself is the instrument. The goal of terrorism involves achieving outcomes like death or destruction, while intent focuses on creating a particular impact (Başeren, 2006). According to these parameters, we can define terrorism as a violent act with political elements that affect the lives of several people and that target reaching certain outcomes like death or dominating people through fear. Similar definitions can also be seen in the works of (Crenshaw, 1981; Hoffman, 2006; Laqueur, 1999; Sandler, 2014; Schmid, 2005). In the contemporary world, terrorist activities, said to be motivated by religious doctrine have gained a global dimension. This is attributed to the general perception today, that global terrorism is fueled by religious doctrines more than ever (Coady, 2021). In this context, we would like to examine terrorism and its relationship with religion. After evaluating the intersection of both concepts, we will direct our focus on the Islamic religion and try to answer the question of whether Islam or its doctrines lay the ground for terrorism.

Religion and Terrorism

Making a definite definition of religion is quite a complicated task. While trying to define religion, we must evaluate the different perspectives used in defining this concept. Different fields of science have tried to define religion in its own phase but how effective, objective, or comprehensive can this definition be for all religions? Generally, we can classify the definitions of religion into two categories: Human-centered and God-centered definitions (Latif, 2021). The Human-centered definitions emphasize that religion is a product of human society and culture. This method is typically used by academics in disciplines including psychology, sociology, and anthropology. They concentrate on the cultural, psychological, and social roles of religion. However, the God-centered approach basically revolves around the belief in a supernatural being (s) (Latif, 2021). Moreover, while defining religion from the God-centered perspective, we need to examine the monotheistic and polytheistic approaches because what one approach regards as religion might not be valid for the other (Schilbrack, 2022).

Nevertheless, despite the differences observed in these definitions, every major religion in the world has always made peace a common goal and called for global fraternity among all humanity. The three Semitic faiths of Judaism, Christianity, and Islam emphasize that promoting harmony and peace both inside and between various religious groups reaps significant benefits in the afterlife. In contrast, Ahimsa, or non-violence, forms a cardinal principle of almost all Aryan religions, like Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism (Anjum, 2017). Each religion offers its adherents guidance on interpersonal engagement, promoting peace and conflict avoidance. However, it is evident that the earliest instances of terrorism in human history occurred under the guise of religion. To examine the reason behind this contradiction, the human, socio-political, and economic factors must be subjected to analysis. Throughout the history of religious conflicts, it appears that humans don't live up to the ethical standards advocated by their respective religions (Khanam, 2014). The politicization of religion can be used as an instrument by anyone to achieve their goals and interests. The drawing of an integral relationship between any religion, especially Islam, and attaching it to terrorism can be a misleading thesis. Terrorism should be understood as a social phenomenon that happens as a result of certain negative conditions of life in places where religion may be instrumentalized as a motivation (Fahd, 2024). Therefore, the ethical teachings of a certain religion might be ignored by its followers due to varying interests.

According to Terzi (2016, pp. 162–172), the roots of terrorism can be categorized into two parameters: subjective and objective reasons. Cultural and socio-psychological aspects are considered subjective causes, whereas misgovernance, frail democratic institutions, poverty, wealth disparity, ignorance, intellectual stimulation, and awakening are considered objective factors. However, it is important to note that the distinction between objective and subjective is not fixed, as what one group perceives as objective may be regarded as subjective by another. According to this classification, the roots and causes of terrorism do not stem from religion but have socio-economic, political, psychological, and cultural dimensions. The attachment of Islam to terrorism by academics also can be seen when they use concepts like “Islamic Terrorism” (Snow & Byrd, 2007; Venkatraman, 2007; Walther & Christopoulos, 2015), “Islamic extremism,” (Simons, 2016) or “Jihadism,” trying to conflate religious identity with violent political acts. This framing tends to oversimplify the complexities of terrorism and overlooks the broader geopolitical and socio-economic factors that contribute to radicalization. Critics frequently point out that the association of Islam with terrorism by using concepts like these reinforces false preconceptions

and fails to acknowledge the political, social, and economic forces behind terrorist activities. These concepts represent Western political and academic counter-terrorism discourse. However, studies have shown that the politicization of the concepts mentioned above does nothing less than manipulate the minds of people and damage community relations (Jackson, 2007).

Religious Doctrine as a Catalyst for Terrorism

Terrorism, mostly justified by religious doctrine, has expanded to a worldwide scale in contemporary times. This can be said to be a result of the 9/11 terrorist attack carried out by al-Qaeda in the USA. The aftermath of the attack has reinforced the perception of religiously motivated terrorism with a global impact (Biçer, 2018). While analyzing the relationship between religion and violence, it is of great importance to take the ideological context in addition to the socio-political grievances into account. In this sense, religious ideology and religion should not be confused with one another. Given that religious ideology deals with the social application and politicization of religious ideas, religion, on the other hand, is mostly focused on ethical advice, spiritual rituals, and worship (Williams, 1996). Religious ideologies frequently take the shape of political ideologies, cultural identities, and societal governance systems. Religion does not inherently lead to violence; rather, what is often perceived as religious violence is influenced by a range of factors beyond religion, such as political, economic, and social grievances (Kirazoluğu, 2021).

The function of ideology is to validate the actions done by its advocates. Ideology serves three key purposes, as highlighted by (Badey, 2002): they polarize and mobilize groups towards specific aims, instill a sense of security through established norms and values, and offer rationalizations for behavior. The basis of political, economic, and social institutions is formed by ideological sentiments, not religion. Although, the shortcomings of these institutions tend to compel certain groups to look for change. The radicals who are seeking change perceive it as a sacred obligation to utilize different types of power including military, media, and politics to fulfill their sentiments (Kirazoluğu, 2021).

In this regard, religion is not the motivation of terrorism, rather, ideologies influenced by various factors are the instigators of violence. Badey (2002) argued that ideologies that are justified by religion have taken over the global terrorism sphere today because other ideologies like communism and nationalism have failed to achieve their desired objectives. According to Ninalowo (2007, p. 152), all religions in the world aim to provide a peaceful and happy livelihood for their adherents. He argues that no religious sentiment promotes killing people or destroying their belongings. He emphasizes that the causes of violence must be traced back to the factors leading to a negative livelihood in the lives of humans. Terrorism and religious extremism are not exclusive to any one religion. People from a wide range of theological backgrounds have justified violent crimes by misinterpreting their beliefs. Every instance has its own historical and political background, and the people or organizations involved frequently twist their religious doctrine to further their own political, nationalist, or personal agendas. In modern times, different pseudo-religious adherents have perpetrated several attacks on human lives, properties, and national peace. Describing Islam as a religion that fuels terrorism by referring to the terrorist activities perpetrated by individuals who identify as Muslims is contradictory to the nature of Islam. When we examine the universal message of Islam in its broad sense, it becomes evident that its ultimate objective is to promote peace (Yılmaz, 2017).

The use of such misrepresentations, if not driven by ulterior motives, suggests a profound lack of understanding on the part of those employing them. Terrorism is a crime against humanity, and it is highly problematic to associate it with any religion (Ninalowo, 2007). Not only is this association incorrect, but it is also fundamentally incompatible with the principles of Islam.

This contemporary age has witnessed the continuous emergence of terrorist groups operating under the guise of Islam. These groups instrumentalize the Islamic Teachings to suit their political or ideological goals (Fahd, 2024). Jihad, a critical term distortedly used today by these groups to justify their acts of violence is often mistranslated especially by the media as “holy war”. However, unlike Judaism and Christianity, Islam has no scriptural approval for holy war (Barlas, 2003). Therefore, attempting to understand jihad through the lens of “holy war” overshadows the distinctive nature of Islam and especially Qur’anic formulations of jihad. The term, as used in the Qur’an connotes two meanings: the greater jihad and the lesser jihad. The greater jihad is a struggle against oneself and the mind. This refers to moral and ethical struggles, including but not limited to the soul, faith, pen, and tongue (Qur’an 29:69; 2:218; 9:20; 25:52; 3:186; 2:177).

The lesser jihad signifies self-defense or fighting against oppression, with strict moral conditions and not initiating violence (Qur’an 22:39-40; 2:190-193; 8:61). However, some extremists misinterpret selective lines like “fight in God’s cause” to justify their terrorist activities. Whereas they ignore the contexts, which emphasize justice and forbid compulsion in religion (Qur’an 2:256), encourage peaceful coexistence with non-Muslims (Qur’an 60:8), and condemns the unjust killing of any person (Qur’an 5:32). The Qur’an consistently emphasizes restraint and fairness, even in war, and it warns against injustice and urges fair dealings regardless of conflict (Qur’an 5:8). Comprehensively reading the Qur’an within its historical and textual contexts, shows that warfare is permitted only in defense, and not as an aggressive means to end religious differences. We would like to use ISIS and Boko Haram as our case study to understand the intersection between extremist religious sentiments and socio-political dynamics.

Religious Doctrine as Justification: The Example of ISIS

The role of ideology in the complex terrain of contemporary terrorism is crucial. Although political factors have a significant influence on ISIS's operations, examining the religious discourse of the group is profound in comprehending its goals and tactics. This chapter will briefly examine how ISIS selectively politicizes verses from the Qur’an to create a legitimate ground for its ideological paradigm. In a bid to examine the motives behind terrorist groups, instrumentalizing religion for their own personal or political interests, we need to understand the concept of “religious exploitation”. According to Diyanet (2018, p. 5), religious exploitation means the deliberate manipulation and distortion of religious doctrines, concepts, and values, used to deceive people in order to gain material or spiritual benefits, in other words, using religion for one's own interests

(Gerges, 2016). Examples of groups like these are the *Khārijites*, who pretended to be defending the Qur’an but happened to be the cause of one of the greatest tragedies in Islamic history. Similarly, the extreme *Shiite* sects called the *Ghulāt* and groups such as *Qāḍiyānūsm*, *Bābūsm*, *Bahā’īsm*, and *Druzeism* argue that their ideologies are legalized by the Qur’an (DİB, 2018). Today, religious exploitation has led to a global security concern that threatens not only the Islamic community but the

whole world. Terrorist organizations such as ISIS, al-Qaeda, Boko Haram, etc., which claim to uphold and represent pristine Islam, cause the greatest harm to Muslims across the world, threaten the future of the Muslim youth and commit corruption and bloodshed all over the globe. Various research has been done on the organizational structure, ideology, and domain of the so-called “Islamic State of Iraq and Syria” (ISIS), otherwise known as the “Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant” (ISIL), sometimes called by their Arabic acronym, DAESH, or just IS, which refers to “Islamic State”. We will be examining the ideological justification of the group based on the studies that have been done. Before proceeding, it is deemed appropriate to introduce the nature and objectives of the group. ISIS, an Islamist Militant group that gained momentum in 2014 after its successful operation in capturing significant territories in Iraq and Syria is known for its literal interpretation of Qur’anic texts. The group’s origin can be traced back to al-Qaeda in Iraq, which was led by Abu Musa al-Zarqawi in the early 2000s (Kirazoluğu, 2021). The violence of ISIS was mostly regional before it declared a caliphate under its self-proclaimed leader Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi and gained international notoriety. After declaring the caliphate, ISIS reached its peak by intensifying its brutalities, mass killings, and public executions to enlarge its territories and claim overall control. Characterized as one of the most dangerous terrorist organizations in the 21st century, ISIS has been known for exploiting regional instabilities, globally spreading its ideologies, recruiting foreign fighters through social media, and placing its sub-divisions in various parts of the world (Oosterveld et al., 2017).

The ideology behind the actions of ISIS cannot be considered as the product of a religious understanding or an interpretation of the Islamic texts because, if ISIS and similar organizations had emerged in a region where another religion is practiced, they would have instrumentalized that religion too (DİB, 2018). The pseudo-religious discourse that has been put forward by this group is the instrumentalization of religion into violence for different purposes. ISIS manipulates religious texts to gain support for its actions and ideology, which are fundamentally rooted in treachery and rebellion (DİB, 2016). A critical issue is that, in deploying these pseudo-religious arguments, the group disregards established religious rules and principles, and it constructs an opportunistic structure shaped to serve its interests. When citing Qur’anic verses and hadiths, ISIS distorts them by stripping them from their original context, neglecting the surrounding passages and relevant scriptural evidence. This selective interpretation damages the broader objectives of religion, which leads to an exploitation of sacred texts that fail to account for their true intent and holistic meaning (Jacoby, 2024). ISIS sought to legitimize its existence as an Islamic-based organization by attaching itself to the early generation of Muslims known as the Salaf al-Salih, However, the ideology of ISIS is rooted in Wahhabism (DİB, 2016).

The literal approach of ISIS to the verses of the Qur’an, ignoring the wisdom and ethical dimensions of Islam has led to a rigid and hostile worldview. Such a fragmented approach to religion, which favors form over substance, is destructive and superficial rather than constructive and profound. ISIS claims that holding democratic elections in Türkiye is not suitable and against Islamic principles (DİB, 2018). The group justifies this by quoting the Qur’anic verse 7:54, “Indeed, to Him belongs the creation and the command.” Even though this verse speaks of God’s cosmic sovereignty rather than a politic-related issue. Contrary to what ISIS claims, several other verses of the Qur’an highlight humanity’s role as God’s caliphs in governing. Moreover, ISIS consistently instrumentalizes the concept of “jihad”. The group promotes a superficial and selective reading of the Qur’an without examining the context behind the revelations of its verses or scholarly guidance. Abu al-Bara al-Hindi, an ISIS figure, exemplifies this

approach by instructing followers to read jihad verses literally, ignoring scholarly interpretations. This flawed approach turns jihad from a duty for maintaining peace into a tool for radicalizing individuals and it illustrates the group's distorted and dangerous understanding of religious texts (Elekberov, 2016). ISIS is known for adopting an exclusionary stance towards other Muslim communities who are not in support of its ideology. They consider anyone who doesn't adhere to their authority or radical sentiments as a *kafir* (Gerges, 2016), and they also justify killing those they accuse of apostasy with their doctrines. Although different factions of ISIS (such as ISIS-K, ISWAP, and others) may exhibit variations in their operational tactics and local adaptations, they fundamentally share similar radical and extremist views toward religion.

Socio-Political Grievances Driving Terrorism: The Example of Boko Haram

While there are significant socio-political grievances associated with the emergence, interests, and organizational structure of ISIS, its pronounced emphasis on representing Islam is particularly noteworthy (Hegghammer, 2010). Consequently, this study utilizes Boko Haram as a case study for examining socio-political grievances. Although Boko Haram also articulates radical religious discourse, it lacks the systematic approach evident in ISIS's ideology and operation (Yahaya, 2016). Albeit various theories like Relative Deprivation Theory (Gurr, 1970), State Weakness and Failure Theory (Rotberg, 2010), Social Identity

Theory (Tajfel & Turner, 2001), Greed vs. Grievance Theory (Collier, 2004), Political Opportunity Theory (Tarrow, 2022) etc., have been developed by different scholars in order to explain the patterns of intrastate violence and social insecurity, it has also been argued that there is not yet an adequate theory that comprehensively addresses the issue of terrorist groups, many of which often adopt pseudo-religious narratives to justify their actions and recruit followers. These narratives can overshadow the elementary socio-political grievances, and they can lead to a misunderstanding of the motivations behind such groups. The Boko Haram phenomenon cannot be explained by a single theory because it emerges from a mix of socio-economic, political, pseudo-religious, and criminal factors. Combining theories can allow for a more comprehensive understanding. It appears that many people have directed their respective opinions, relying on the religious propaganda adopted by Boko Haram to attribute Islam as the group's primary motivation (Olofinbiyi & Steyn, 2018). While various studies have effectively disproven the pseudo-religious ideologies propagated by the group, there remain significant misunderstandings and biases within both academic circles and the public regarding Islam. Moreover, it is crucial to emphasize the socio-economic and political grievances that underpin the group's actions (Fahd, 2024). A comprehensive approach to addressing these factors is necessary to better understand the root causes of such extremism.

The prevailing view worldwide has often been that the terrorism of Boko Haram in Nigeria is primarily motivated by religious factors rather than by socio-economic issues. However, a study done by Olofinbiyi & Steyn (2018) reveals that the emergence of Boko Haram was basically a response to the pervasive corruption and decades of poor administration, specifically in the Northern Region and in Nigeria as a whole. Political deterioration and socioeconomic exploitation, in combination with unfulfilled demands resulting from the denial of fundamental human rights, systemic decay, impoverishment, and ineffective democratic procedures in the northern parts of Nigeria contributed

immensely to the rise of Boko Haram. In his other study, Olofinbiyi (2018) argues that Boko Haram uses Islam as an instrument of justification for their malicious acts and terrorist attacks. Moreover, as a platform from which the group releases their resentment and anger about the socio-economic inequalities and political grievances. Initially, Boko Haram didn't emerge as a terrorist organization, nor did it advocate for an insurgency (Fahd, 2024). It started as a mini-religious group in Northern Nigeria under the name Yusufiyya, adopting a radical interpretation of Islam that rejected Western education and influences. However, it is essential to acknowledge the economic and socio-political factors that stimulate this movement and contribute to its ability to attract followers. When the state fails to meet its responsibilities in providing employment, shelter, and basic physiological needs, the emergence of groups that claim the right to these necessities becomes inevitable (Olofinbiyi, 2018). Such groups often advocate for change by taking advantage of existing social frameworks, such as religious organizations and community networks, as justifications for their actions (Mustapha, 2014). In the case of Boko Haram, its followers, influenced by the stale Almajiri education system, instrumentalize Islam to achieve their goals. This educational system, combined with the socio-economic challenges faced by its followers and the political interests of its leaders (Agbibo, 2015), not only exacerbates their vulnerabilities but also facilitates the recruitment strategies employed by the group. It is crucial to also emphasize that recruitment into groups like Boko Haram stems not only from a single factor. Studies have revealed that the majority of the people joining terrorist groups are affected by various socio-economic, cultural, psychological, and political factors (Bamidele, 2016). Considering these factors collectively and integrating them into the analysis of the root causes of terrorist groups can provide valuable guidance in addressing this thesis.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The history of terrorist acts carried out in the name of religion predates the 9/11 attacks. The first religious ideology-motivated terrorist attack in history can be traced back to the 1st century A.D. The term terrorism, which has evolved multifariously throughout history, is generally perceived today to be motivated by religious sentiments. However, this study has revealed that religion in its nature advocates harmony, peace, interpersonal engagement, and conflict avoidance. These principles hold a fundamental and significant place across all religious traditions. The inhumane acts of terrorist groups, justifying their violence with religion, are evidence that people often fail to uphold the ethical standards laid down by their respective religions. This study has deduced that the motivations driving pseudo-religious extremist groups extend beyond mere unilateral interpretations of religious doctrines, it encompasses a range of socio-political, economic, psychological, and cultural factors. Terrorist groups such as ISIS and Boko Haram have carried out numerous attacks targeting both Muslims and non-Muslims, often justifying their actions using terms like "jihad" or establishing an "Islamic State." As its name implies, ISIS seeks to legitimize itself through claims to Islamic teachings. However, studies have consistently shown that ISIS's actions fall far short of the ethical principles upheld by Islam. While the group's religious ideology is prominent, it is important to recognize that political dimensions also play a significant role in its emergence.

On the other hand, Boko Haram, as its name suggests, arose largely in response to the socio-political and economic instability in Northern Nigeria, which was exacerbated by widespread corruption among local authorities. The group attributes these problems to Western influences and democratic systems. In

this context, if Boko Haram had emerged in a different region where Islam is not a dominant influence, a similar uprising could still occur; however, it would likely be justified by other ideologies rather than religious sentiments. Historical examples of such uprisings can be seen in movements rooted in ideologies like communism or nationalism, where grievances against socio-political or economic conditions led to significant resistance or rebellion. The identities of ISIS and Boko Haram as militant extremist groups are shaped by a variety of interrelated factors, which include ideology, socio-political grievances, and strategic ambitions. The ideological motivations of both groups are similar and originate from a perverted understanding of jihad, which they instrumentalize to justify violence and pursue political goals. Moreover, the impact of local grievances on their emergence, recruiting strategies, and modus operandi must be considered when analyzing each group. Based on these findings, the concepts used to identify these and other pseudo-religious extremist groups, especially in the media and academia, could be reviewed. Postcolonial theorists regard translation as a political instrument that can be used to subjectively buttress or question existing concepts fashioned by their adversaries. ISIS, instead of being translated simply as the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria, could more accurately be referred to as the 'so-called' or 'pseudo-Islamic State of Iraq and Syria.' This terminology emphasizes that the group does not represent ethical Islamic teachings but rather distorts religious concepts to justify its violent activities. The conformation of terms such as “religious terrorism”, “Islamic terrorism”, “jihadist extremism” or “Islamist militancy” etc. falls within this scope. It is crucial to challenge the legitimacy of these labels by clarifying that groups like ISIS misuse Islamic concepts, such as jihad, which in its true sense encompasses a broad range of meanings, including personal spiritual struggle, and not merely violent conflict. Moreover, it is more accurate to characterize these groups as "violent extremist groups", "militant organizations claiming Islamic justification", or “extorters of religion” It is crucial to understand that the formation of these organizations is frequently fueled by a confluence of socio-political variables, such as economic hardship, political instabilities, and complaints against perceived injustices. This multifarious approach challenges the stereotypes that connect terrorism with Islam as a religion by shifting the focus from religious belief alone to the broader factors that stimulate the growth of extremism.

References

- Agbibo, D. E. (2015). The social dynamics of the “Nigerian Taliban”: Fresh insights from the social identity theory. *Social Dynamics*, 41(3), 415–437. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02533952.2015.1100364>
- Amir, P. (2024). *Alamut'un Efendisi Hasan Sabbah*. Truva Yayınları.
- Anjum, M. R. (2017). Concept of Peace in World's Major Religions: An Analysis. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14003.66088>
- Anti-Defamation League, A.-D. L. (2012). *Anti-Abortion Violence: America's Forgotten Terrorism*. <https://www.adl.org/resources/news/anti-abortion-violence-americas-forgotten-terrorism>
- Badey, T. J. (2002). The Role of Religion in International Terrorism. *Sociological Focus*, 35(1), 81–86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00380237.2002.10571222>

- Bamidele, O. (2016). Combating Terrorism: Socioeconomic Issues, Boko Haram, and Insecurity in the North-East Region of Nigeria. *Military and Strategic Affairs*, 8(1).
- Barlas, A. (2003). Jihad, Holy War, and Terrorism: The Politics of Conflation and Denial. *American Journal of Islam and Society*, 20(1), 46–62. <https://doi.org/10.35632/ajis.v20i1.516>
- Başeren, S. (2006). Uluslararası şiddet ve terörizm ders notları. *Ankara Üniversitesi*.
- Biçer, R. (2018). Why Muslims Become Instruments of Terror? *Kader*, 16(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.18317/kaderdergi.389900>
- Coady, C. A. J. (2021). Religion, War, and Terrorism. In C. A. J. Coady (Ed.), *The Meaning of Terrorism* (p. 0). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780199603961.003.0009>
- Collier, P. (2004). Greed and grievance in civil war. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 56(4), 563–595. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oep/gpf064>
- Crenshaw, M. (1981). The Causes of Terrorism. *Comparative Politics*, 13(4), 379–399. <https://doi.org/10.2307/421717>
- DİB, D. İ. B. (2016). *Dini İstismar ve Tedhiş Hareketi*. https://yayin.diyaret.gov.tr/File/Download?path=331_1.pdf&id=331
- DİB, D. İ. B. (Ed.). (2018). *DEAŞ dehşete dayalı bir din istismarı* (2. baskı). Diyanet İşleri Başkanlığı.
- Elekberov, F. (2016). Günümüz İslam Dünyası'nda Meseleler ve Çözüm Yolları: Uluslararası sempozyum. In C. Bayram (Ed.), *Türk-İslam Dünyasının Yeni Çözüm Yolu: Türklük, İslamlık ve İnsanlık* (pp. 323–358). Türk Ocakları İstanbul Şubesi.
- Eroğlu, A. H. (2004). Farklı İnanıcı Tehdit Olarak Algılamının Sonucu Engizisyon Terörü. *Dini Araştırmalar*, 7(20), Article 20.
- Fahd, A. (2024). The Distorted Ideology of Boko Haram: Jihad or Terrorism? *Journal of Analytic Divinity*, 8(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.46595/jad.1409244>
- Gatade, S. (2014). Pawns In, Patrons Still Out: Understanding the Phenomenon of Hindutva Terror. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 49(13), 36–43.
- Gerges, F. A. (2016). *ISIS: A history*. Princeton University Press.
- Gurr, T. R. (1970). *Why men rebel*. Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315631073>
- Hegghammer, T. (2010). The Rise of Muslim Foreign Fighters: Islam and the Globalization of Jihad. *International Security*, 35(3), 53–94.
- Hoffman, B. (2006). *Inside Terrorism* (REV-Revised, 2). Columbia University Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7312/hoff12698>
- Horsley, R. A. (1986). The Zealots. Their Origin, Relationships and Importance in the Jewish Revolt. *Novum Testamentum*, 28(2), 159–192. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1560435>
- Islam, S. S. (1997). The tragedy of the Babri Masjid: An expression of militant Hindu fundamentalism in India. *Journal of Muslim Minority Affairs*, 17(2), 345–351. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13602009708716382>

- Jackson, R. (2007). Constructing Enemies: 'Islamic Terrorism' in Political and Academic Discourse. *Government and Opposition*, 42(3), 394–426. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1477-7053.2007.00229.x>
- Jacoby, T. (2024). The Islamic State's use of the Qur'an in its Magazines, Dabiq and Rumiya. *Discourse & Society*, 35(3), 345–359. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09579265231208660>
- Khanam, D. F. (2014). *The Study of Worlds Major Religions* (1st edition). Goodword.
- Kirazoluğu, O. (2021). Religiously Motivated Terror Discourse (Daesh Case). *Savunma Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2(40), 83–105. <https://doi.org/10.17134/khosbd.1001188>
- Laqueur, W. (1999). *The New Terrorism: Fanaticism and the Arms of Mass Destruction*. Oxford University Press.
- Latif, T. (2021). Din Felsefesi Nedir? In T. Latif (Ed.), *Din Felsefesi* (pp. 19–21). Bilay.
- Linton, M. (2023). Jacobins and Terror in the French Revolution. In *The Cambridge History of the Age of Atlantic Revolutions: Volume 2: France, Europe, and Haiti* (Vol. 2, pp. 225–246). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108599405.011>
- Mahir, T., & Serkan, Y. (2019). Terrorism. In *International Security* (pp. 159–174). Anadolu University.
- Michel, L., & Herbeck, D. (2001). *American Terrorist: Timothy McVeigh and the Oklahoma City Bombing*. HarperCollins.
- Mustapha, A. R. (2014). Understanding Boko Haram. In *Sects & Social Disorder: Muslim Identities & Conflict in Northern Nigeria* (NED-New edition, pp. 147–198). Boydell & Brewer.
- Ninalowo, A. (2007). *On the crisis of underdevelopment* (1st Edition). First Academic Publishers,.
- Olofinbiyi, S. A. (2018). *Socio-economic context of Boko Haram terrorism in Nigeria*. [Doctoral Dissertation, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban.]. <https://researchspace.ukzn.ac.za/handle/10413/18560>
- Olofinbiyi, S. A., & Steyn, J. (2018). The Boko Haram Terrorism: Causes Still Misunderstood. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(1), 129–144. <https://doi.org/10.3844/jssp.2018.129.144>
- Oosterveld, W. T., Bloem, W., Farnham, N., Kayaoğlu, B., & Sweijts, T. (2017). *The Rise and Fall of ISIS: From Evitability to Inevitability*. The Hague Centre for Strategic Studies.
- Pedahzur, A., & Perliger, A. (2009). *Jewish Terrorism in Israel*. Columbia University Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7312/peda15446>
- Prasse-Freeman, E. (2017). *The Rohingya crisis*. *Anthropology Today*, 33(6), 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8322.12389>
- Rotberg, R. I. (2010). *When States Fail: Causes and Consequences*. Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400835799>
- Sandler, T. (2014). The analytical study of terrorism: Taking stock. *Journal of Peace Research*, 51(2), 257–271. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022343313491277>

Schilbrack, K. (2022). The Concept of Religion. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Summer 2022). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2022/entries/concept-religion/>

Schmid, A. P. (2005). Root Causes of Terrorism: Some Conceptual Notes, a Set of Indicators, and a Model. *Democracy and Security*, 1(2), 127–136.

Schmidt, A. P. (2023). *Defining Terrorism*. International Center for Counter-Terrorism ICCT. <https://doi.org/10.19165/2023.3.01>

Shanice, M. (2019). *The Globalising Nature of Terrorism and The Manifestations and Implications of New Terrorism* [Doctoral dissertation]. University of Pretoria.

Simons, G. (2016). Islamic extremism and the war for hearts and minds. *Global Affairs*, 2(1), 91–99. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23340460.2016.1152446>

Snow, D., & Byrd, S. (2007). Ideology, Framing Processes, and Islamic Terrorist Movements. *Mobilization: An International Quarterly*, 12(2), 119–136. <https://doi.org/10.17813/maiq.12.2.5717148712w21410>

Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. (2001). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. In *Intergroup relations: Essential readings* (pp. 94–109). Psychology Press.

Tarrow, S. G. (2022). *Power in movement: Social movements and contentious politics* (Revised and updated fourth edition). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009219839>

Terzi, M. (2016). *Din Referanslı Terörizm Üzerine* (1. bsk). Edge Akademi Yayıncılık.

Venkatraman, A. (2007). Religious Basis for Islamic Terrorism: The Quran and Its Interpretations. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 30(3), 229–248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10576100600781612>

Walther, O. J., & Christopoulos, D. (2015). Islamic Terrorism and the Malian Rebellion. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 27(3), 497–519. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546553.2013.809340>

Williams, R. H. (1996). Religion as Political Resource: Culture or Ideology? *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 35(4), 368–378. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1386412>

Yahaya, A. (2016). Boko Haram and Islamic State of Iraq And Syria: The Nexus. *Polac International Journal of Humanities and Security Studies*, 2, 299–312.

Yılmaz, Y. (2017). Barış'ın İslam'ın Temel Kaynakları ve İslam Tarihi'ndeki Yeri. *FSM İlmî Araştırmalar İnsan ve Toplum Bilimleri Dergisi*, 375–397. <https://doi.org/10.16947/fsmia.372674>